

Motivations to Respond Without Prejudice and Ethnic Outgroup Attitudes in Late Childhood:
Change and Stability During a Single School Year.

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Abstract

This longitudinal study (three waves across a school year) investigated the links between children's motivations to respond without prejudice and their ethnic outgroup attitudes at the between-person level (means and changes over time) and the within-person level (time-specific fluctuations). Participants were 945 ethnic majority students ($M_{ageWI} = 9.86$ years, $SD = 1.21$; 471 girls) from 51 grade 3–6 classrooms in the Netherlands. Children reported (increasingly) more positive outgroup attitudes when their internal motivation was structurally high (between-person effects) and temporarily high (within-person effect), and less positive attitudes when their external motivation was structurally and temporarily high. The between-person effects were independent of the ethnic composition and the antiprejudice climate of the classroom. These findings may help in developing interventions aimed at reducing prejudice in late childhood.

There is a strong commitment in developmental psychology to contribute to the prevention and reduction of prejudice by examining underlying processes and testing interventions (Beelmann & Lutterbach, 2021; Cooper et al., 2022). Prejudice can be defined as a negative orientation toward people merely based on their group or category membership (see Raabe & Beelmann, 2011), and developmental psychologists have successfully applied concepts and insights from social psychology to study it. For example, by now, there is clear evidence that positive intergroup contact can improve children's outgroup attitudes (Tropp & Prenevost, 2008), that social identity processes play a role in children's intergroup relations (Killen & Rutland, 2011), and that implicit group attitudes can be measured in children as well as adults (Baron & Banaji, 2006). However, one social psychological concept that has been rather neglected in the developmental intergroup literature is that of motivations to respond without prejudice. People can have internal and external reasons for behaving in nonprejudiced ways, including, respectively, personally held convictions about the wrongness of prejudice, and concerns about approval by others, with different effects on their feelings, attitudes, and behaviors toward outgroup members (Plant & Devine, 1998). These reasons can indicate how individuals process, or have processed, social norms against prejudice, which makes it important to consider them in intervention research. Yet, despite the development and testing of many interventions to reduce prejudice and improve intergroup relations in children (see for example, Beelmann & Heinemann, 2014) and a large, informative body of literature on children's reasoning about outgroup exclusion (to be discussed below), we know very little about their motivations to respond without prejudice.

The present research addressed this gap in the literature by investigating those motivations in a large sample of ethnic majority children and studying their links with children's outgroup attitudes within and across three waves in a single school year. The participant children were in late childhood (age 7-13) which is an important period for the promotion of

positive intergroup relations: Group attitudes are becoming more dependent on social contexts than (Raabe & Beelmann, 2011), and children are increasingly able to see that others can belong to multiple categories at the same time implying more flexible ways of dealing with group boundaries (Aboud & Amato, 2001). Our study took place in the Netherlands, and we focused on ethnic Dutch majority students (grades 3-6) and their attitudes toward Turkish and Moroccan peers. People of Turkish and Moroccan descent constitute the largest non-Western immigrant-origin groups in the country: On January 1 2018 - which fell in the time span of our study – the proportions of first- and second-generation Turks and Moroccans in the Netherlands amounted to, respectively 2.3 % and 2.5% of the Dutch population, and to 17.7 % and 18.0% of the non-Western immigrants (Statistics Netherlands, 2022). Although Turks and Moroccans differ in many respects, they are considered minorities in Dutch society, facing relatively high levels of prejudice and discrimination (Andriessen, 2017). Moreover, research has shown that Dutch majority children evaluate Turkish and Moroccan peers quite similarly, and as less positive than their ethnic ingroup (e.g., Thijs, 2017).

Internal versus External Motivations to Respond without Prejudice

Two common assumptions in the social psychological research on prejudice are that there is a basic, automatic tendency to be prejudiced which is acquired at a very young age and needs to be suppressed or regulated (Devine, 1989; see also, Dunham et al., 2008), and that the expression of prejudice is generally considered to be unacceptable (Crandall et al., 2002). Those assumptions indicate that it is important to study individuals' motivations for responding without prejudice, and to examine their concerns with social (dis)approval as part of these motivations. In doing so, several social psychological studies (with adults) (for recent examples, see Bamberg & Verkuyten, 2021; LaCosse & Plant, 2020) have used Plant and Devine's (1998) distinction between two motivations to respond without prejudice: an internal one and an external one. The internal motivation (IM) involves a desire to be nonprejudiced which is based

on personal standards, and people who have this motivation are convinced that avoiding prejudice is important and the right thing to do. In contrast, the external motivation (EM) to be nonprejudiced reflects concerns with social standards. Thus, externally motivated people want to conform to antiprejudice norms to avoid disapproval by others (Plant & Devine, 1998).

Both motivations are relatively independent which means that they can operate at the same time. Thus, people may try to be nonprejudiced to prevent social scorn, also if they personally believe that prejudice and discrimination are wrong. Still the effects of the two motivations are markedly different, because it is easier and more natural to regulate prejudice if this is considered to be personally relevant and valuable, but more difficult and tiresome if one feels pressured to do so (see Legault et al., 2007). Moreover, because the pressure to live up to the nonprejudiced standards of others can make people feel threatened and angry it could create attitudinal backlash, and as such even increase the expression of prejudice (Plant & Devine, 2001). Accordingly, research in adults has convincingly shown that the IM is more effective in regulating prejudice than the external one. It appears that the former is associated with explicit positive outgroup attitudes in both private and public situations, and with less outgroup anxiety and less implicit prejudice, i.e. automatic negative attitudes that are harder to control than explicit attitudes. In contrast, the EM is related to positive outgroup attitudes in public but not in private situations, and to more outgroup anxiety and more explicit and implicit prejudice (Butz & Plant, 2009; Devine et al., 2002; Hausmann & Ryan, 2004; LaCosse & Plant, 2020; Plant, 2004; Plant & Devine, 1998).

Additionally, there is some evidence that both motivations can interact. The nature of these interactions appears to depend on the particular outcome variable (see Butz & Plant, 2009) but the IM has been found to diminish the impact of the EM on privately reported explicit prejudice (Plant & Devine, 1998; Plant et al., 2003). The latter finding implies that the EM to

regulate prejudice is least effective in the absence of internalized reasons to be nonprejudiced (IM).

Children's Prejudice and Motivations to Respond without Prejudice

There is clear research evidence for an increase in explicit prejudice (or bias) from early to middle childhood which levels off afterwards (for a meta-analysis, see Raabe & Beelmann, 2011), and developmental theories such as Social-Cognitive Developmental Theory (SCDT; Aboud, 2008) and Social Identity Development Theory (SIDT; Nesdale, 2004) state that there are specific age-related changes in children's group attitudes. SCDT claims that prejudice peaks around age 7, due to children's cognitive limitations (including the inability to categorize persons along multiple dimensions) and their attentional focus on groups rather than individuals, but that it diminishes afterwards (Aboud, 2008). SIDT also holds that group bias increases until age 7. Yet unlike SCDT, it conceives of this bias as ingroup preference and attributes it to a focus on the ingroup. It states that, after this age, children are also outgroup focused and can develop prejudice, but not necessarily so, depending on their ingroup identification, threat, and perceived norms (Nesdale, 2004). Despite their emphasis on developmental changes in children's explicit attitudes, both SCDT and SIDT hold that the categorical thinking necessary for prejudice is present at a young age already (see Degner & Wentura, 2010). Relatedly, there is convincing evidence for an early emergence of implicit group bias (age 3), which is presumably due to an early exposure to stereotypes and appears to be invariant from childhood to adulthood (Dunham et al., 2008, 2013). Thus, although children's development enables them to have less explicit bias after middle childhood, they still have an automatic tendency to be prejudiced, just as adults. Hence, it is meaningful to examine the motivations to respond without prejudice in late childhood (age 7-13).

Other developmental work has provided indications that these motivations can be internal as well as external in children. For example, many studies in the developmental

intergroup literature have used Social Cognitive Domain Theory (Smetana, 2006) to examine how children in late childhood and adolescence reason about group-based exclusion. This research has convincingly shown that, although children sometimes condone this exclusion based on social conventional reasoning (including arguments related to group functioning), they typically reject it based on moral grounds (concerns with harm and fairness) (Cooley et al., 2019; Killen et al., 2016; Rutland & Killen, 2015). However, research has also shown that children as young as six appear to be motivated to hide their group biases (Rutland et al., 2005) and disinclined to openly disadvantage others based on their ethnic or racial group membership (De França & Monteiro, 2013). Thus, in late childhood, there is a clear awareness that prejudice is both morally wrong and socially unacceptable.

Hughes et al. (2016) were the first to demonstrate that the IM and EM to respond without prejudice can be measured in 7-to-12-year-olds. These researchers adapted the original measures by Plant and Devine (1998) and administered them to different samples of (mostly) White American children in individual interviews. They found that the IM to respond without prejudice was associated with more positive and less negative attitudes toward African Americans, and with less intergroup anxiety. In contrast, the EM was associated with more intergroup anxiety, but unrelated to children's group attitudes (Hughes et al., 2016).

Another study also applied the internal-external distinction to examine motivations to respond without prejudice in ethnic majority children, but in that study, children completed anonymous questionnaires in their classroom (Masked Reference). The authors used a newly developed measure that differed in two respects from that by Hughes et al. (2016). First, the measure contains language that is arguably easier to understand for children. It does not include the terms "prejudice" and "stereotypes", which can be abstract to children (see Hughes et al., 2016), but instead asks them about their reasons for "acting nice to children from other countries or cultures." It uses a positive formulation ("acting nice"), as indicating disagreement with

negatively worded items (e.g., “not acting mean”) can be rather complex for children (Marsh, 1986). Although acting nice involves more than not acting mean, it does imply it, and research on the so-called positive-negative asymmetry effect suggests that childhood prejudice is more likely to manifest as a lack of positive behavior than as the presence of negative behavior (Rutland et al., 2007).

Second, consistent with a self-determination perspective on prejudice regulation (Legault et al., 2007), the measure assesses intrinsic appreciation for outgroup contact as an additional aspect of children’s internal motivation to be nonprejudiced. Thus, the IM subscale not only reflects internalized beliefs about the importance of equality and positive behavior toward outgroup children, but also the desire to know them and interact with them. Jargon and Thijs (2021) found that the antiprejudice motivations of ethnic majority children had distinct effects on their privately reported ethnic outgroup attitudes, and these effects were similar for 3rd-4th graders and 5th-6th graders. The effect of the IM was strong and positive, and although the effect of the EM was smaller, it was negative and thus counterproductive. The present investigation builds on that research by combining its cross-sectional data with two extra waves to examine the relations between children’s motivations to respond without prejudice and their outgroup attitudes at the between-person level, but also at the within-person level, which has not been done before. As we will argue below the distinction between these levels is important for thinking about interventions. Our study also makes a new contribution by examining whether the classroom context moderates the relations between motivations and attitudes at the between-person level.

Stability, Change, & Interactions with Context

Knowing whether children’s antiprejudice motivations change over time could be crucial for attempts to improve intergroup relations, especially during middle and late childhood when prejudice is increasingly context dependent (Raabe & Beelmann, 2011). However, there

is lack of developmental research, and the existing social psychological work on adults typically focuses on between-person differences that are assumed to be relatively stable. For example, Plant and Devine (1998) reported relatively strong autocorrelations for their internal and external scales over a nine-week period (respectively, 0.77 and 0.60) and presented this as support for the reliabilities of those measures. Still, research has shown that people's antiprejudice motivations can be influenced by experimental manipulations (Legault et al., 2011), and meaningfully predicted by other variables when their autocorrelations are controlled for (Kunstman et al., 2013, Study 1; Plant, 2004). Thus, despite their relative stability, these motivations seem to be malleable, at least in adults, and the same might hold for children.

To fully appreciate the potential importance of antiprejudice motivations for children's interethnic relations it is important to go beyond the between-person level and to include the within-person level as well (cf., Miklikowska et al., 2019). In the present research, we did this by making the distinction between the individual means in these motivations (aggregated over time) and the time-specific fluctuations around those means. As a result, we could address the between-person question of whether stable differences in antiprejudice motivations are related to mean levels and growth (positive or negative) in outgroup attitudes, but also the within-person question of whether temporal changes in children's outgroup attitudes correspond to temporal changes in their motivations. Arguably both questions are relevant to understand children's group attitudes. However, the within-person question is essential to determine whether antiprejudice motivations might be targeted in interventions to improve intergroup relations: If the changes in children's group attitudes would be unrelated the changes in their motivations, it would not make any sense to improve the former by influencing the latter.

Because many antiprejudice interventions with children take place in schools (Beelmann & Lutterbach, 2021) and the school context is relevant for children's ethnic attitudes (e.g., Schwarzenhal et al., 2018), it is also important to know whether the between-person links

between their motivations and outgroup attitudes are similar for children in different classrooms. Classrooms can vary in terms of ethnic composition and the degree to which teachers stimulate a normative climate that condemns prejudice (Verkuyten & Thijs, 2013), and both factors might directly influence children's motivations to be nonprejudiced (see Kunstman et al., 2013; Jargon & Thijs, 2021; Plant, 2004). Yet, another important issue is whether they moderate the impact of children's motivations once they have developed them. It might be argued that this contextual moderation is more likely for EM than IM, as the former involves concerns with the social environment whereas the latter involves personal convictions and intrinsic appreciations. Still, just like their external counterparts, those internal reasons might be more salient in some contexts than in others.

In less ethnically homogeneous classrooms, children are more exposed to diversity, and this could make questions about their behaviors toward ethnic others more relevant for their daily lives. This could mean that the links between children's antiprejudice motivations and outgroup attitudes are stronger in those classrooms. Likewise, it could be expected that children's antiprejudice motivations have more relevance for their outgroup attitudes in classrooms where teachers frequently emphasize that prejudice is wrong. Even though internally motivated children have probably already internalized the norm to be nonprejudiced, this contextual emphasis might strengthen the impact of the IM by making antiprejudice concerns more salient. In a similar vein, it could be assumed that children's worries about violating antiprejudice norms are more pressing and salient in classrooms where teachers put more emphasis on them leading to stronger negative effects of EM in those classrooms (see Plant & Devine, 2001).

Summary and Hypotheses

Despite a large literature on the development and prevention of childhood prejudice, very little is known about children's motivations to respond without prejudice. With the present

study, we sought to make a unique contribution by examining the relations between those motivations and children's outgroup attitudes during the course of a single school year (cf., Váradi et al., 2021). In doing so, we made the distinction between the between-person level and the within-person level, and we also examined the impact of classroom ethnic composition and antiprejudice climate. We anticipated that the IM would be positively related to children's outgroup attitudes whereas the EM would be negatively related to them. Specifically, at the within-person level, we expected that children who were temporarily more internally motivated would temporarily report more positive outgroup attitudes than they normally did (Hypothesis 1.1), and that children who were temporarily less externally motivated would report less positive outgroup attitudes (Hypothesis 1.2). Likewise, at the between-person level, we expected a positive relation between children's mean IM and their mean outgroup attitudes (Hypothesis 2.1), and a negative relation between their mean EM and their mean outgroup attitudes (Hypothesis 2.2). However, for the between-person level, we could test additional hypotheses related to the growth in children's outgroup attitudes over time. Children's mean antiprejudice motivations might also gradually affect their attitudes toward ethnic others, by affecting their direct or indirect engagement with those ethnic outgroup peers. An IM implies more openness and willingness to learn about outgroups, and children's growing familiarity with ethnic others can increase their positivity toward them (e.g., Tropp & Prenevost, 2008). Similarly, an EM may increasingly turn children away from ethnic others (see Hughes et al., 2016) which could worsen their ethnic attitudes. Hence, we also tested whether children's mean IM was associated with increased outgroup positivity over time (Hypothesis 3.1), and whether their mean EM was related to decreased outgroup positivity over time (Hypothesis 3.2).

Based on earlier research findings (Plant & Devine, 1998; Plant et al., 2003), we also tested whether the interactions between the two motivations were positive at the within-person level and the between-person level (Hypothesis 4), that is to say, whether the IM at each level

diminished the (anticipated) negative impact of the EM at the corresponding level. Lastly, we examined whether the between-person relations between children's motivations and outgroup attitudes depended on the classroom context. We expected that that the anticipated links would be stronger in classes with less ethnic homogeneity (Hypothesis 5) and classes with a stronger normative climate against prejudice (Hypothesis 6). In testing the effects of the motivations we controlled for gender differences as there are some indications that girls report more outgroup positivity than boys (e.g., Geerlings et al., 2017), and because research among adolescents (14-18-year-olds) found girls to have stronger internal prejudice motivations (Thijs et al., 2016). To make sure that the (anticipated) relations between children's motivations and outgroup attitudes were not due to their gender, we added it as a control variable.¹

Method

Participants and Procedure

This study was part of a larger research project on teachers' and students' dealings with diversity which was approved of by the Ethics Review Board of the third author's institution (project no. 2017-CDE-8653). It includes data collected in 32 primary schools in the Netherlands during the fall (Wave 1), winter (Wave 2), and spring (Wave 3) of the school year 2017-2018, with at least two months between each wave. The project focused on grade 3-6 classes, and all children in each class were eligible for participation. Originally, 1439 children participated by completing surveys in their classrooms under supervision of a researcher or research assistant who was available to answer questions from the children. The survey was titled "My class and me" and included questions related to ethnicity and cultural diversity, as well as classroom relations and academic engagement. During each wave, teachers provided questionnaire data as well, but those were not included in the present study. Informed passive

¹ We also controlled for children's age, but in an additional set of analyses, because our earlier study found that the motivation measures were metrically but not scalarly invariant for younger versus older children. Results are available on request and indicate that our findings cannot be explained by age differences.

parental consent was obtained for all participating children. We used the information from the original sample ($N = 1439$) to construct our contextual variables (ethnic classroom composition and antiprejudice classroom climate) but for our analyses involving antiprejudice motivations and ethnic attitudes we only selected children who could be identified as Dutch (see “Ethnic background”). This final sample of Dutch participants consisted of 945 children (471 girls and 474 boys, with a mean self-reported age of 9.86 years ($SD = 1.21$) at Wave 1) from 51 classrooms. For these children, the percentage of missing values on the motivation and attitude measures ranged from 5.7% to 12.1%. Little’s MCAR test suggested that the missing data patterns was completely at random, $\chi^2(397) = 428.926, p = 0.13$.

Measures

Ethnic background. At each of the three waves, children were asked about their own ethnicity and the ethnicities of their mother and father, but they were permitted to skip these questions in 36 classes at Wave 3 to diminish the burden of data collection. First, they were presented with the following description: “In the Netherlands, there are different cultural groups. Those groups have to do with the country where people or their families come from. For example, you have Turks, Moroccans, Surinamese, but also Dutch and many more.” Next, they were asked to indicate what groups their mother, their father, and they themselves belonged to. Response categories included Turks, Moroccans, Surinamese (the three largest non-Western minority groups in the country), and Dutch, and a remaining category where other groups could be listed. Children could also choose more than one category. The Dutch participants for the present study were selected in two steps. First, we took those children who identified themselves, their mother, *and* their father as Dutch only during at least one of the waves ($n = 952$). Second, we found that seven children in this selection reported (partly) Turkish or Moroccan identities (for themselves or their parents) at one or more of the other waves. Because we focused on Turks and Moroccans as ethnic outgroups, we removed those children from the

selection.

Antiprejudice motivations. Children’s motivations to respond without prejudice were measured with a new instrument, which we based on earlier research among adults (Plant & Devine, 1998; Legault et al., 2006). This instrument assesses children’s endorsement of different reasons for “acting nice toward children from other countries or cultures” and consists of an IM scale and an EM scale. The IM scale has five items (“because I want to get to know these children”, “because I think that everyone is equal”, “because I think it is important to be nice to everyone”, “because I like to”, and “because I find it wrong to be mean to them”) and the EM scale has four items (“because other people expect me to”, “because otherwise people will think I am mean”, “because I am afraid that otherwise people will get angry with me”, and “because otherwise people might think I am a bad child”). All items are rated on a five-point scale ranging from “No!” (1) to “Yes!” (5). Previous analyses of the Wave 1 data (Masked Reference) supported a model in which the IM and EM items loaded on two different factors that were weakly correlated and metrically invariant across children from the earlier (3-4) versus the later grades (5-6). In the present study we examined whether this factor structure was invariant over time (see preliminary analyses below). The internal consistencies of both scales were satisfactory. For IM, the Cronbach’s alphas were 0.76, 0.79, and 0.83 at Waves 1, 2, and 3, respectively. For EM, these alphas were 0.80, 0.82, and 0.84.

Ethnic group attitudes. To assess children’s ethnic attitudes, they were asked to evaluate, Moroccan, Turkish, and Dutch children, respectively, on three traits. These measures have been successfully used in previous research in the Netherlands (Thijs, 2017). For the present study we only used the evaluations of Turkish and Moroccan children. The participants had to estimate whether most of the children in each group were, “honest”, “fun to play with”, and “eager to help”, and the response scale ranged from “No, certainly not!” (1) to “Yes, certainly!” (5). At each wave, the three items for each group evaluation loaded on a separate

factor (see preliminary analyses below), but the two factors were strongly related at each wave ($r_s > 0.79$). Thus, we combined the evaluation items in a six-item outgroup attitudes scale, for which Cronbach's alpha was 0.90 at Wave 1, 0.91 at Wave 2, and 0.93 at Wave 3.

Ethnic classroom composition. Our measure for ethnic classroom composition reflected the proportion of students who identified themselves, their mother, *and* their father as completely Dutch during at least one of the waves not counting the students reporting (partly) Turkish or Moroccan identities at one or more of the other waves.

Antiprejudice climate. To assess children's perceptions of the antiprejudice climate they were asked to rate how often their teacher made the following statements: "You should be nice and honest to people from other cultures", "It is wrong to be mean to people from other countries", and "People from all cultural groups are equal". These items were based on research on multicultural education in the Netherlands (see Verkuyten & Thijs, 2013), and the response scale ranged from "Absolutely never!" (1) to "Very very often!" (5). For the present study, we used the available responses of *all* participating students (including those of different or mixed ethnicities) to obtain a reliable classroom aggregate. First, we calculated scale scores at the individual level. Cronbach's alpha was 0.81 at Wave 1, 0.83 at Wave 2, and 0.86 at Wave 3 for these individual responses. Next, we calculated two intraclass correlations (ICC's) to examine the degree to which students' perceptions were consensual (ICC1) and the degree to which classmates' perceptions formed a reliable aggregate (ICC2) (Lüdtke et al., 2009). For all waves, ICC1 exceeded 0.198 indicating that more than 19.8% of the variance in individual perceptions could be attributed to different classrooms and hence teachers. ICC2 was 0.85 at Wave 1, 0.86 at Wave 2, and 0.86 at Wave 3 indicating high agreement among classmates. Thus, we averaged the available responses in each classroom, and as these aggregated scores were considerably related across waves ($r_s > 0.78$) we calculated a mean score for which Cronbach's alpha was 0.93.

Data Availability Statement

The data described in this article are openly available in the Open Science Framework at <https://osf.io/t4xmq/>.

Results

Preliminary Analyses

Factor structure and measurement invariance. Our main analyses were conducted on observed variables (scale scores) rather than latent factors, and longitudinal measurement invariance was a prerequisite for them. Thus, we first conducted a set of confirmatory factor analyses in Mplus version 8.3 (Muthén & Muthén, 1998-2017) to examine the factor structure underlying our motivation and attitude measures and to test whether this structure was metrically and scalarly invariant over time. We examined all measures simultaneously, and to avoid estimation problems due to having more parameters than clusters we did not take the classroom clustering into account. First, we tested a configural (unconstrained) model in which the wave-specific items for each scale loaded on one corresponding factor per wave, and which the errors for each item were allowed to correlate between waves. After allowing two cross-factor error correlations within each wave (between the item “honest” for the attitude toward Moroccan children and the attitude toward Turkish children, and between the item “eager to help” for each attitude), the model fit was adequate, $\chi^2(828) = 1833.858$, CFI = 0.957, TLI = 0.949, RMSEA = 0.036 (90% CI [0.034, 0.038]), SRMR = 0.038 (see Kline, 2011). Next, we examined the metric and scalar invariance across time by constraining, first, the factor loadings and, next, the intercepts across waves. The fit of both models was acceptable, respectively, $\chi^2(850) = 1858.645$, CFI = 0.957, TLI = 0.950, RMSEA = 0.035 (90% CI [0.033, 0.038]), SRMR = 0.039, and $\chi^2(880) = 1988.565$, CFI = 0.953, TLI = 0.947, RMSEA = 0.037 (90% CI [0.034, 0.039]), SRMR = 0.042. Although the χ^2 difference test was highly significant ($p < 0.001$) for the comparison of the scalar and the metric model (but not the metric versus the

configural model $p = 0.31$), the differences in CFI were < 0.05 , and the differences in RMSEA and SRMR were < 0.01 . Hence because there was no “appreciable change in practical fit indexes” (Widaman et al., 2010, p. 13) we relied on the more conservative criteria by Chen (2007) and considered our measures as invariant over time (see also Putnick & Bornstein, 2016).

Intercorrelations and means. Table 1 shows the intercorrelations and descriptive statistics for the study variables. The stability in children’s antiprejudice motivations and outgroup attitudes across waves was relatively strong ($0.46 \leq r \leq 0.71$). Next, children’s internal and external antiprejudice motivations were rather independent from each other and differentially related to children’s ethnic attitudes. At each time point, the internal motivation was associated with more outgroup positivity whereas the external motivation was associated with less outgroup positivity. The correlations were stronger for the internal motivation.

Next, girls were more internally motivated and (generally) less externally motivated than boys, and more positive toward the outgroups. Moreover, participants in more homogeneous classrooms (higher proportion of ethnic Dutch students) were less internally motivated at Wave 1, but also less externally motivated at Waves 1 and 3, and students were more positive about the two outgroups at Wave 3 if there was a strongly emphasized antiprejudice norm in their classroom.

Table 1 also shows that the mean scores for external motivation were relatively low (below the scale midpoint) and that the mean scores for internal motivation and outgroup attitudes were relatively high (above the scale midpoint, $ps < 0.01$ for one sample t-tests).

Main Analyses

We used multilevel modeling in Mplus 8 (Muthén & Muthén, 1998-2018) to test whether children’s antiprejudice motivations would predict their outgroup attitudes at the within-person level (Level 1) and at the between-person level (Level 2). In addition to this, we included a third

level representing the differences between classrooms. The within-person effects in our analyses represent the associations between the within-person fluctuations in children's antiprejudice motivations (i.e., the deviations from their personal over-time means) and the within-person fluctuations in their outgroup attitudes (ibidem). The between-person effects, by contrast, involve the relations between children's mean antiprejudice motivations over time (which were grand-mean centered in the analyses) and the over-time mean and change (slope) in their outgroup attitudes. We built our model in various steps, and we used deviance test (Δ -2LL) and the AIC criterion to evaluate model improvement (see Kreft & de Leeuw, 1998).

Fluctuations and change over time. We started by building a random-intercept model to examine the fluctuating and stable components of children's outgroup attitudes (see Table 2, Step 1). Please note that this model included three levels: the within-person level (Level 1) and the between-person level (Level 2) but also the classroom level (Level 3) as children were nested in their classrooms. Results showed that 59% of the variance in outgroup attitudes was between children and 2.5% between classrooms. This means that 38.5% of the variance was at the within-person level, indicating substantial time-specific fluctuations within persons.

Next, we added fixed linear and quadratic slopes to the model to analyze the change in outgroup attitudes over time. Adding these slopes significantly improved the fit of the model. As shown in Table 2 (Step 2) the linear slope was positive and the quadratic slope was negative implying an increase in outgroup positivity followed by a plateau.

In the third step, we randomized the linear slope at the between-person level which led to a significant improvement in model fit. As indicated in Table 2, this slope variance was significant indicating that there were differences between children in the linear rate at which their outgroup attitudes changed over time. Please note that the linear slope variance at Level 3 (between classrooms) was constrained to zero as it proved to be nonsignificant ($b = 0.00, p = 0.759$).

Effects of antiprejudice motivations. In the next step (Step 4) we used children's IM and EM to predict the time-specific fluctuations in their outgroup attitudes at Level 1, and the personal means and changes of their outgroup attitudes at Level 2. We divided children's motivation scores in a stable part (Level 2) by calculating the means across time, and a fluctuating part (Level 1) by centering the time specific scores on the mean scores. Next, we entered the fluctuating parts as predictors of the fluctuations in outgroup attitudes at the within-person level, and the stable parts (over-time means) as predictors of the over-time mean and linear slope at the between-person level. Doing so significantly improved the fit of the model.

As shown in Table 2 (Step 4) children's IM was positively related to their outgroup attitudes at Level 1, which means that their outgroup positivity was higher than usual when their internal motivation was higher than usual as well. EM had a negative effect at Level 1. This effect was marginally significant ($p = 0.078$) but in the expected direction (and significant with one-sided testing). Thus, when children were more externally motivated than usual at a specific time point, they were also somewhat less positive about their outgroups.

At the between-person level (Level 2), children's IM predicted more overall outgroup positivity and a more pronounced increase in outgroup positivity over time. In contrast, EM predicted less outgroup positivity overall, but it was unrelated to the change in outgroup attitude. We also investigated the interactions between the IM and EM at the within-person and between-person levels (Step 5). Adding the interaction terms (three in total) did not significantly improve the fit of the model and there were no significant interactions at the between-person level. However, the interaction was significant and negative at the within-person level indicating that the temporal positive effect of children's being more internally motivated than usual was undermined by their temporal EM².

² We calculated the between- and within-person scores for the two motivations based on the available data. However, for 53 of the 941 cases, there was only one measurement available for (one of) the motivation measures, implying within-person scores of zero. Hence, we repeated our analyses from Step 4 onward for first, the 898 cases with at least two available measurements for each motivation measure, and second, the 703 cases with three measurements of both motivations. Results are available at <https://osf.io/t4xm9/> and comparable to those

Moderating effects of ethnic classroom composition and norms. Lastly, we conducted two analyses to test whether the obtained between-person effects of children's motivations were moderated by the ethnic composition of their classroom and the consensually perceived antiprejudice norms of their teacher. The non-significant interaction between both motivations at the between-person level was dropped in these analyses.

First, we examined the cross-level interactions for children's IM. That is to say, we predicted the effects of this motivation on the mean and linear slope of children's outgroup attitudes from the proportion of ethnic Dutch students and the perceived teacher norms in their classroom. The main effects of these contextual variables were included as well. Results showed that these main effects were not significant, $p > 0.15$. Moreover, the effects of IM on the mean and slope of children's attitudes were not moderated by ethnic composition, respectively, $b = 0.35$, $p = 0.17$, and $b = -0.10$, $p = 0.50$, or perceived teacher norms, respectively, $b = 0.13$, $p = 0.15$, and $b = 0.02$, $p = 0.77$. Next, we followed the same procedure for the between-person effect of EM on the over-time mean of children's outgroup attitudes. Again, neither ethnic composition nor the perceived teacher norms moderated this effect, respectively, $b = -0.13$, $p = 0.42$, and $b = -0.04$, $p = 0.50$, although there was a marginally significant main effect of the perceived teacher norms in this analysis, $b = 0.09$, $p = 0.086$,

In sum, none of the cross-level interactions between the two motivations and ethnic classroom composition and perceived teacher norms were significant. This indicates that the effects of these motivations were independent of those classroom- and teacher characteristics.

Discussion

The goal of the present study was to examine the relations between children's motivations to respond without prejudice and their ethnic outgroup attitudes. We used a longitudinal design in

reported in the text. However, in the second set, the within-person effect of EM (Step 4) was no longer marginally significant ($p = .194$), and the within-person interaction between IM and EM (Step 5) was marginally significant, $p = .086$. In both sets, ethnic composition now moderated the between-person effect of IM on the mean, $p < .05$.

which we examined those relations at the between-person level and the within-person level, and tested whether they depended on the ethnic composition and antiprejudice climate of children's classrooms. Our results showed that there was both change and stability in children's motivations to respond without prejudice across the school year. Moreover, both the fluctuating and the stable parts of their motivations were related to their ethnic outgroup attitudes. Consistent with our hypotheses, children were temporarily more positive about Turkish and Moroccan peers when their internal motivation was temporarily strong (within-person association), and both structurally more positive about these outgroup peers and increasingly positive over time if they were structurally more internally motivated (between-person association). Children's external motivation showed fewer and weaker relations to their outgroup attitudes. At the between-person level, children's EM was unrelated to the change in outgroup attitudes over time, yet negatively related to children's overall attitudes. Next to this, we found, at the within-person level, that children who were more externally motivated than they usually were, were temporarily less positive about their outgroups, but also, unexpectedly, that there was a negative rather than a positive interaction between the two motivations. We return to this finding below. Lastly, we found that the between-person effects of children's motivations did not depend on the classroom's ethnic composition or antiprejudice climate, which indicates that they are relatively robust.

It is important to connect our findings to the existing developmental literature on intergroup relations, and more specifically, the large work on children's reasoning about group-based exclusion. Social domain research has shown that children typically use moral reasoning to reject this exclusion, but sometimes condone it based on social conventional reasoning (Cooley et al., 2019; Killen et al., 2016). Both types of reasoning are contrasted as they involve different types of considerations: concerns with fairness and harm, and concerns with group functioning and social norms and traditions, respectively (see also, Yoo & Smetana, 2022).

However, as indicated by Social Identity Development Theory (SIDT; Nesdale, 2004) and the subjective group dynamics model (Abrams et al., 2003) – two approaches that have been (recently) integrated with Social Cognitive Domain Theory (see Cooley et al., 2016) – group norms can also contribute to the rejection of group-based exclusion when they are inclusive rather than exclusive. Social norms can also emphasize moral considerations, which raises the question whether children adhere to antiprejudice norms because they personally endorse them, or because they fear the negative consequences of violating them (or both). To the best of our knowledge, our study is one of the very few to directly address this question by examining children’s IM and EM to be nonprejudiced. Still, our findings that children had a relatively strong IM to respond without prejudice is consistent with social domain research showing that children generally regard group-based exclusion as morally wrong.

As mentioned, the negative interaction between the two motivations at the within-person level was unexpected and contradicts previous social psychological evidence that individuals’ IM inhibits the counterproductive effects of their EM on privately reported prejudice (Plant & Devine, 1998; Plant et al., 2003). Instead, it suggests that being temporally externally motivated can reduce the positive effect of being temporally internally motivated. We do not have a clear-cut explanation for this result, but the fact that it differs from earlier findings among adults suggests a developmental interpretation. More specifically, two factors could play a role here. First, the negative social consequences of appearing prejudiced that externally motivated persons want to avoid, might ultimately be more threatening for children than for adults. After late childhood and early adolescence the normative impact of peers and parents wanes (Berndt, 1979; Fuligni et al., 2001; Steinberg & Monahan, 2007), and this might explain why concerns with others’ negative reactions no longer undermine the positive impact of the IM on explicit prejudice in adulthood. Second, the unexpected interaction may indicate that responding without prejudice is more difficult for children than for adults. There is very

little literature on prejudice regulation in children, but research on 5-9-year-olds suggests some age-related differences in the skills that underly that regulation (Hoyo et al., 2019). Importantly, our interaction result corresponds to findings obtained for implicit prejudice among adults (Devine et al., 2002) and implicit prejudice is more difficult to control than explicit prejudice. Although we examined children's explicit ethnic attitudes, they might find those harder to regulate than adults. Thus, their EM may hamper the impact of their IM, and this might change when they grow older. For now, this interpretation is merely tentative and future research is needed to test it.

Together, our results show that it is important that children are nonprejudiced for the "right" reasons. From a prejudice-reduction perspective, it is clearly more desirable if children try to be open and nice toward outgroup peers because they find this important, valuable, and inherently interesting, than if they do so to avoid social scorn and negative reactions by others. However, both motivations were found to be statistically unrelated in our sample, which indicates that they are not mutually exclusive and can be simultaneously active. Thus, even if children are internally motivated to be nonprejudiced (either structurally or temporarily) they can be concerned about the negative social consequences should they fail at this. As indicated by our findings, such concerns could counteract and, at the within-person level, diminish the positive effects of their IM. Still, it is important to note that the effects of the IM were stronger than those of the EM. This means that children who scored high on both motivations were still more open to others than children who scored low on each of them.

Our findings are potentially relevant for attempts to reduce prejudice and improve intergroup relations in children, not only in the school environment, the context of the present study, but also at home. In theory, children's motivations to respond without prejudice could play two different roles in such interventions: These motivations could be directly targeted in order to make children more accepting of, and open to outgroup others, but to the extent that

that this is difficult, interventions could also take into account that children with different motivations could react differently to attempts to improve their group attitudes.

In thinking about the first possibility, it is important to note that, although the within-person and the between-person differences examined in this study were statistically independent, the fluctuations we observed could very well contribute to between-person differences over longer periods of time. The fact that there was both change and stability in each motivation, corresponding to change and stability in children's outgroup attitudes, makes them excellent candidates for this. Their fluctuations suggest that they are amenable to influence, and their stability suggests that such influence might have enduring effects. An important question then, is how to stimulate children's internal motivation to respond without prejudice without focusing their attention on the social unacceptability of prejudice. The answer to this question is beyond the scope of the present study, but based on Self-Determination Theory it can be expected that children will be more internally and less externally motivated if their basic needs for autonomy, relatedness, and competence are met (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Teachers (Niemic & Ryan, 2009) and parents (Grolnick et al., 1997) could satisfy these needs by generally providing autonomy support, emotional support, and structure, respectively. Yet they could also attend to them in what and how they communicate to children about intergroup relations and prejudice (see Pahlke et al., 2021). Experimental research among adults has shown that the nature of antiprejudice messages affects whether they are effective or rather counter effective. More specifically, people can become more internally and less externally motivated to respond without prejudice when provided with choice and explanations, but the opposite can happen when they are urged to combat prejudice and to comply with social norms against it (Legault et al., 2011). Likewise, parents and teachers could be trained to acknowledge children's need for autonomy, by giving them convincing reasons to be open to ethnic others or let them discover those reasons themselves. Indeed, students who have teachers initiating

deliberative discussions in ethnically diverse classrooms are more positive toward ethnic diversity (Miklikowska et al., 2022). Moreover they could support children's sense of competence and relatedness by teaching them that it is possible to control one's prejudiced tendencies but also that everyone has those tendencies and that making mistakes in intergroup interactions does not necessarily make one a bad person (Thijs, 2022). In fact, research has shown that children who believe that prejudice is not a fixed individual quality are more open to cross-racial interactions (Pauker et al., 2022).

In addition to this, high-quality contact with ethnic outgroup peers could play an important role. The internal motivation measure did not only involve children's internalized beliefs about the importance of equality and positive behavior toward outgroup others, but also assessed children's intrinsic appreciation for outgroup contact as a reason for outgroup positivity. Positive contact experiences could stimulate this appreciation (Binder et al., 2009), and schools and parents could be encouraged to provide the conditions for those experiences. For example, a supportive and cooperative atmosphere in ethnically diverse classrooms stimulates greater openness toward ethnic diversity by (among others) facilitating trust toward other people (Miklikowska et al., 2019; Miklikowska et al., 2021). It is important to note, in this regard, that the larger opportunities for intergroup contact in diverse schools or classrooms do not guarantee positive interaction with outgroup others (Thijs & Verkuyten, 2014). And although children in less homogeneous classrooms (lower proportion of ethnic Dutch students) were more internally motivated at Wave 1, they were also more externally motivated at Waves 1 and 3.

Second, as mentioned, school-or parent-based antiprejudice interventions could also take into account children's existing motivations to respond without prejudice and try to stimulate conditions that make the IM more relevant and the EM less relevant. Discovering such conditions is an important task for future research. Unexpectedly, the between-person

effects obtained in our analyses did not depend on the classroom's ethnic composition or antiprejudice climate. However, there may be other important contextual or individual moderators. An interesting possibility is that factors that directly influence children's motivations, could also affect the very impact of those motivations. There is evidence, for example, that the pressure to comply with pro-diversity norms has stronger negative effects among individuals who are primarily externally motivated to respond without prejudice (Plant & Devine, 2001). Moreover, consistent with Social Identity Development Theory, experimental research found that children were more prejudiced when there was a peer group norm of exclusion and when there was threat from the outgroup (Nesdale et al., 2005). It is reasonable to expect that individual differences in motivations to respond without prejudice also matter more in those situations. For example, children who are externally but not internally motivated might show more prejudice when their peers condone outgroup exclusion.

In evaluating the present findings, it is important to consider some limitations and qualifications, and further suggestions for future research. First, it is important to note that our conclusions about stability and change depend on the number of measurement occasions, three waves, and the time span under investigation, a period of about 6-7 months. With more waves, we would have probably obtained more reliable estimates of the stable components of children's motivations and attitudes, although their correlations over time were quite substantial already (≥ 0.46). Likewise, we would probably have observed more change over a longer period, such as multiple school years.

Second, we focused on one specific group of children (ethnic Dutch children) in relation to two specific outgroups (Turkish and Moroccan peers combined). Turks and Moroccans are considered as typical ethnic minority groups in Dutch society, and that ethnic Dutch children's evaluations of them correlate to their evaluations of other ethnic minority groups (van Bommel et al., 2020). Still, it remains to be seen whether similar effects can be obtained among other

groups and in other national contexts. More specifically, it is important to examine anti-prejudice motivations and their effects in children from ethnic minority groups. This was not possible with the present dataset, which included attitudes toward Turkish, Moroccan, and Dutch children, and too few participants from the first two groups – which also prevented us from creating a non-skewed classroom composition measure that reflected their presence in the classroom. Related to this, future research could examine how minority children who are the targets of negative group evaluations react to majority children’s motivations to respond without prejudice, to better understand the meaning of prejudice from the victim’s perspective.

Third, we asked children about their reasons for “acting nice to children from other countries or cultures” rather than responding without prejudice. Although we did so for reasons of understandability, demonstrating outgroup positivity (“acting nice”) is not identical to *not* showing outgroup prejudice. Still, the former implies the latter, and childhood prejudice typically manifests as a lack of positive behavior (Rutland et al., 2007). Moreover, the exhortation to be nice, is often coupled with the exhortation not to be mean as indicated by the internal consistency of the perceived antiprejudice climate measure, which included both of them. Thus, we believe that our measure was appropriate for studying children’s motivations to respond without prejudice.

Fourth, children could have other motivations to respond without prejudice that were not captured by our instrument, for example, the desire to challenged inequalities (internal) or the desire to have social status and prestige (external). Still, the internal consistencies of the scales were acceptable indicating that they represented the underlying domains sufficiently well.

Lastly, our study completely relied on self-reports. Although motivations and attitudes can hardly be measured in other ways, self-reports could be affected by social desirability considerations. We tried to minimize the impact of these concerns by facilitating anonymous

responding, stressing confidentiality and asking children to answer as honestly as possible. Moreover, to the extent that these considerations reflect stable individual tendencies they could have only affected the between-person findings.

Prejudice and group hostility are timely societal problems, and late childhood is a crucial time to prevent these problems and promote positive intergroup relations. Yet, although several interventions have been proposed and tested to reduce and prevent prejudice in that period (Beelmann & Heinemann, 2014; Beelmann & Lutterbach, 2021), and despite a considerable body of work on children's prejudice (Raabe & Beelmann, 2011) and reasoning about group-based exclusion (e.g., Cooley et al., 2019; Killen et al., 2016; Rutland & Killen, 2015), children's motivations to respond without prejudice have been neglected in the developmental literature so far. Despite its limitations and the work still to be done, the present study tried to make a unique to the literature by examining these motivations and their between- and within-person links with children's ethnic outgroup attitudes. We found that children are and become more positive toward ethnic others if they find this personally relevant and attractive, but not if they want to be nonprejudiced to avoid disapproval. It is our sincere hope that these findings can contribute to the promotion of harmonious ethnic relations in children and future adults.

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Table 1.

Intercorrelations and Descriptive Statistics

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	<i>n</i>	M (SD)
1. Internal Motivation W1												891	3.91 (0.75)
2. Internal Motivation W2	0.57**											843	3.93 (0.77)
3. Internal Motivation W3	0.50**	0.60**										832	3.93 (0.83)
4. External Motivation W1	0.06	0.06	0.05									890	2.25 (1.00)
5. External Motivation W2	-0.04	0.06	0.01	0.49**								841	2.19 (1.00)
6. External Motivation W3	-0.03	0.04	0.09**	0.46**	0.52**							831	2.11 (1.01)
7. Outgroup Attitude W1	0.45**	0.37**	0.37**	-0.14**	-0.14**	-0.12**						889	3.38 (0.90)
8. Outgroup Attitude W2	0.40**	0.56**	0.51**	-0.11**	-0.13**	-0.12**	0.64**					851	3.56 (0.87)
9. Outgroup Attitude W3	0.36**	0.46**	0.59**	-0.10**	-0.09**	-0.10**	0.54**	0.71**				847	3.62 (0.92)
10. Gender (girl 0.5 vs boy -0.5)	0.18**	0.21**	0.20**	-0.08*	-0.06	-0.07*	0.17**	0.18**	0.16**			945	0.00 (-)
11. Ethnic Composition	-0.32*	-0.08	-0.12	-0.30*	-0.18	-0.32*	0.22	-0.14	-0.03	-0.24		51	0.75 (0.20)
12. Antiprejudice Climate	0.18	0.11	0.21	-0.11	-0.21	-0.20	0.17	0.21	0.31*	-0.17	-0.23	51	2.45 (0.46)

Note. Ethnic composition and antiprejudice climate were correlated with aggregated versions of the other variables.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Table 2

Multilevel Model Results for the Prediction of Children's Outgroup Attitudes

Model Steps	Model Fit	Δ -2LL (df)	Within-person Effects (Level 1)	Between-person Effects (Level 2)	Variance Level 1	Variance Level 2
Model 1 Unconditional	LL (df) = -2954.07 (4) AIC = 5916.14 BIC = 5939.58	-	-	-	0.314**	0.479**
Model 2 Fixed Linear and Quadratic Slope	LL (df) = -2910.04 (6) AIC = 5832.08 BIC = 5867.23	88.06 (2)**	$b_{\text{linear}} = 0.23^{**}$ $b_{\text{quadratic}} = -0.06^*$	-	0.298***	0.485**
Model 3 Random Linear Slope	LL (df) = -2877.49 (8) AIC = 5770.98 BIC = 5817.84	65.10 (2)**	$b_{\text{linear}} = 0.23^{**}$ $b_{\text{quadratic}} = -0.06^{**}$	-	0.215**	0.643**
Model 4 Predictors: Internal and External Motivations at Level 1 and Level 2	LL (df) = -2471.87 (16) AIC = 4975.73 BIC = 5068.92	811.24 (8)**	$b_{\text{linear}} = 0.21^{**}$ $b_{\text{quadratic}} = -0.05^*$ $b_{\text{Internal}} = 0.29^{**}$ $b_{\text{External}} = -0.03$	$b_{\text{Internal}_{\text{mean}}} = 0.64^{**}$ $b_{\text{Internal}_{\text{slope}}} = .060^{**}$ $b_{\text{External}_{\text{mean}}} = -0.17^{**}$ $b_{\text{External}_{\text{slope}}} = 0.00$ $\text{Cov}_{\text{mean*slope}} = -0.08^{**}$	0.202**	0.427**
Model 5 Interaction between Internal and External Motivations at Level 1 and Level 2	LL (df) = -2469.30 (17) AIC = 4976.59 BIC = 5097.26	5.14 (3)	$b_{\text{linear}} = 0.21^{**}$ $b_{\text{quadratic}} = -0.05^*$ $b_{\text{Internal}} = 0.29^{**}$ $b_{\text{External}} = -0.03$ $b_{\text{Int*Ext}} = -0.09^*$	$b_{\text{Internal}_{\text{mean}}} = 0.65^{**}$ $b_{\text{Internal}_{\text{slope}}} = 0.06^{**}$ $b_{\text{External}_{\text{mean}}} = -0.18^{**}$ $b_{\text{External}_{\text{slope}}} = 0.00$ $b_{\text{Int*Ext}_{\text{mean}}} = 0.04$ $b_{\text{Int*Ext}_{\text{slope}}} = -0.01$ $\text{Cov}_{\text{mean*slope}} = -0.08^{**}$	0.202**	0.425***

Note. LL= lower limit; AIC=Akaike information criterion; BIC =Bayesian information criterion. Due to missing values all models involve 941 children. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$